

**EFFECT OF BLADE LOADING DISTRIBUTION ON AXIAL COMPRESSOR FLOW
STABILITY WITH INCREASING TIP CLEARANCE**

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ABSTRACT

The evolutionary trend of modern aeroengines, coupled with operational factors such as wear, leads to an increase in relative tip clearance (TC) size, which consequently deteriorates flow stability within the compressor. This degradation primarily manifests as a reduction in stall margin (SM) and a significant enhancement of unsteady flow effects near the rotor tip, such as Rotating Instability (RI). The impacts of different blade loading distribution (BLD) designs (fore-loaded, Origin; after-loaded, AL) on the flow stability of a low-speed compressor are investigated, across a range of TC sizes from 0.6% to 3.0%. Within the small TC range, AL consistently enhances full-TC-range SM. This capability stems from its ability to reduce the leading edge loading and promote a more uniform axial distribution of the tip leakage flow (TLF). Furthermore, AL exhibits remarkable desensitization to TC within 0.6% - 0.8% range, as its BLD remains essentially unchanged, resulting in minimal variations in key TLF features. Within the large clearance range, the onset of RI for AL occurs at a significantly lower mass flow rate. Meanwhile, AL reduces the dominant circumferential mode order below the blade count, contributing to a substantial reduction in RI frequency. Concurrently, AL exhibits a superior ability to organize the flow field, leading to a purer RI-related frequency signature and lower corresponding amplitude in the tip pressure spectrum compared to Origin.

Keywords: Tip Clearance, Blade Loading Distribution, Flow Stability, Rotating Instability

1. INTRODUCTION

Higher thrust-to-weight ratios, enhanced efficiency, and reduced fuel consumption rates are primary objectives for modern civil aero-engines, leading to increasing bypass ratios and consequently enlarging the relative tip clearance (TC) in the engine core. Additionally, TC dynamically varies due to rotational centrifugal forces, thermal effects, and blade-casing wear during operation. The impacts of TC variation manifest in steady and unsteady aspects:

1) Steady impacts: conventional studies have indicated that TC enlargement degrades performance, including steady characteristics and stall margin (SM). In terms of pressure rise, a 1% increase in TC reduces peak pressure rise by 4.6% [1]. Regarding efficiency, a 1% increase in TC height diminishes efficiency by 2% [2]. Regarding SM, the stall mass flow rate rises with TC growth, consequently reducing the SM [3]. Notably, some studies revealed non-monotonic change of performance with respect to TC size: an optimal TC size exists for maximal performance. For instance, there is a specific TC corresponding to the largest operation flow range [4].

2) Unsteady impacts: increased TC intensifies complexity and unsteadiness of tip flow, leading to the occurrence of rotating instability (RI). RI further induces phenomena such as non-synchronous vibration, which are closely linked to unsteady tip leakage flow (TLF) dynamics [5] and directly detrimental to compressor safety during operation. Consequently, the study of flow physics within multi-scale TC plays a critical and indispensable role in aero-engine design.

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Prolonged engine in-service time leads to progressive TC enlargement, which is detrimental to SM. Consequently, two critical issues require attention:

1) How to accurately predict compressor stall onset ?

While the diffusion factor [6] and Koch's criterion [7] served as engineering design criteria, their effectiveness is heavily dependent on existing databases, resulting in limited generalizability. To fundamentally understand stall mechanisms, analytical stability models emerged, including linear model such as Emmons model [8] and nonlinear model such as Moore-Greitzer model [9]. However, analytical models involve lots of geometric and flow simplifications in their formulations. With advances in computational science, numerical simulations [10] have been widely adopted for stall onset prediction, but they are heavily influenced by turbulence modeling and computational resources. In 2013, Sun et al. [11] proposed the general theory of flow instability in turbomachinery, and developed simplified models like the meridional surface stability prediction model. Validated in both subsonic and transonic compressors, this method enables rapid and accurate stall inception prediction. Building on Sun's model, Fang [12] improved the solution algorithm and resolved the least stable mode distribution successfully. Crucially, this advancement provides a direct characterization of flow perturbations in the tip region from both modal-pattern and theoretical perspectives. However, studies directly correlate those modes with physical tip flow mechanisms remain relatively scarce.

2) How to enhance SM under varying TCs and maintain the SM, i.e., achieve desensitization to TC ?

Conventional approaches are used in after-design phase, including passive and active control techniques. However, passive control methods exemplified by casing treatments [13] often incur efficiency penalties while enhancing SM. Meanwhile, active control strategies such as the "anti-sound" principle [14] face limitations in response timeliness in engineering. Consequently, optimization in blade design phase serves as the preferred pathway for improving flow instability. Significant progress has been achieved through blade loading distribution (BLD) design. Combining numerical simulations and model predictions, Xu demonstrated that after-loaded blade designs enhance SM in both subsonic [15] and transonic compressors [16], with experimental validation further confirming this effect in a subsonic compressor [17]. Nevertheless, the work of Xu was confined exclusively to the design TC. Consequently, the extent to which after-loaded rotors retain SM-enhancing efficacy under various TCs merits rigorous examination.

Furthermore, addressing the challenge of mitigating performance variations and SM degradation induced by TC changes—i.e., achieving desensitization to TC—remains a critical engineering objective. Sakulkaew [18] numerically investigated TC effects on rotor efficiency in a large-scale industrial gas tur-bine, proposing a blade loading design guidance for performance desensitization to TC: rotor with after-loaded tip and fore-loaded hub, while stator featuring fore-loaded tip and after-loaded hub. Furthermore, Tiralap [19]

improved aforementioned design guidance from a loss-reduction perspective. Contradictorily, Erler [20] demonstrated, through high-speed compressor simulations and theoretical analysis, that rear cambered after-loaded rotor failed to achieve desensitization, and it was more sensitive than the BASE rotor, whereas front cambered fore-loaded rotor demonstrated superior desensitization capability. Thus, the aforementioned BLD designs for performance desensitization to TC demonstrate confliction and remain experimentally unverified. And its efficacy requires rigorous investigation.

The inevitable increase in TC, combined with the pursuit of high blade loading designs, makes the occurrence of RI more likely in aeroengines. In 1985, Mathioudakis et al. [21] first identified distinct spectral peaks different from rotating stall, by frequency analysis of a single-stage axial compressor operating at low mass flow rates. Baumgartner et al. [22] subsequently coined the term "Rotating Instability" and modeled the phenomenon as fluctuating acoustic sources rotating with the rotor. Given that RI is more readily triggered under high blade loading, the pressure field in the blade tip region and the BLD are often employed as primary means for its analysis. Mario et al. [23] conducted tip pressure measurements on a single-stage compressor and found that the propagation speed of RI increases linearly as the flow coefficient decreases, independently of TC size. Ryosuke et al. [24] performed unsteady numerical simulations and experimental measurements on the tip flow field of a multi-stage high-speed axial compressor near surge conditions. Their work revealed that RI is caused by the circumferential propagation of TLV breakdown, and further investigated the effects of varying TCs and tip stagger angles. Although altering the tip stagger angle influences the tip loading distribution, this approach focuses on local geometric modifications rather than a holistic BLD design philosophy.

It is noteworthy that research on SM enhancement and desensitization to TC has involved BLD design considerations. Conversely, while previous studies on RI have often analyzed changes in BLD, few have directly investigated the influence of the BLD design itself. Therefore, this study focuses on the impact of BLD design on flow stability under various TC sizes by integrating numerical simulations, stability model predictions, and experiments. Section 2 briefly describes the test rig, numerical setup, and the stability prediction model. Section 3 presents the findings, segmented by TC size ranges: for small TCs, it examines the mechanisms behind SM enhancement and desensitization achieved through BLD design; for large TCs, it analyzes the effects of BLD design on RI and the underlying causes. Section 4 summarizes the conclusions regarding the influence of BLD design on SM enhancement, desensitization to TC, and RI.

2. METHODS

2.1 Test rig

TA36 is a low-speed single-stage axial compressor, as shown in FIGURE 1. Main design parameters of TA36 are shown in TABLE 1. P1 and P2 denote the pressure measurement sections located at the compressor inlet and downstream of stator

blades, respectively, including static pressure taps and total pressure combs. There are 20 detachable rotor blades in position 1, and 27 stator blades in position 2. To conduct throttling process and control mass flow rates, a throttling device in position 4 (green box) is used to adjust the outlet area. 7 high-frequency pressure transducers (S1 - S7) are uniformly distributed along the axial direction at the rotor tip to capture the unsteady pressure field. Additionally, 17 transducers (C1 - C17) are circumferentially installed upstream of the rotor. Among these, sensors C1 - C8 are evenly spaced around the entire circumference, while sensors C9 - C17 are concentrated within the circumferential sector between C1 and C2. This circumferential array is designed to resolve the dominant circumferential mode order of RI.

FIGURE 1: TA36 SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM

TABLE 1: MAIN DESIGN PARAMETERS OF TA36

Parameter	Value
Rotational speed (rpm)	2930
Number of blades	20 (Rotor) 27 (Stator)
Mass flow rate (kg/s)	7.5
Original rotor tip chord c (mm)	120
Static pressure rise coefficient	0.45
Efficiency (%)	90.5

To reduce costs, casings with varying inner diameters were selected to change TC size. The selected TC sizes are $0.6\%c$ (the design TC size, T06), $0.8\%c$ (T08), $1.2\%c$ (T12), $1.8\%c$ (T18), $2.2\%c$ (T22), and $3.0\%c$ (T30). Experimental results indicate that within T06 - T12, denoted as TC range 1, no significant RI was observed. In contrast, RI emerged among T18 - T30, denoted as TC range 2. Thus, the subsequent analyses in Section 3 are structured accordingly, examining the flow characteristics within these two distinct TC ranges separately.

2.2 Numerical simulation setup

The numerical simulations comprise both single-passage Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) computations and full-annulus unsteady RANS (URANS) computations. The O4H mesh topology was used, as illustrated in FIGURE 2 along with mesh details in the rotor tip and hub regions. The k-epsilon turbulence model was selected, and inlet total temperature was set to 288.15 K and inlet total pressure was set to 101,325 Pa. The height of the first grid layer adjacent to the wall is $5e-6$ m,

yielding a near-wall y^+ value of approximately 1 at the design point (DP).

The single-passage RANS simulations were primarily employed within TC range 1. A mixing plane model was applied at the rotor-stator interface, and the throttling process was achieved by progressively increasing the back pressure at the compressor outlet. FIGURE 3 presents the grid independence study conducted at the design TC, along with a comparison between the numerically simulated steady characteristics and experimental measurements. The medium mesh (1.7 million cells) achieved grid-independent requirement. The static pressure rise coefficient ψ obtained from the single-passage simulation shows good agreement with experimental data, while the predictions of the stall point (SP) mass flow rate fail. Thus, the validation and verification process for numerical setup is considered complete. Within TC range 1, the absence of RI in experimental observations indicates minimal flow unsteadiness, justifying the application of RANS for capturing the fundamental characteristics of the tip flow field.

FIGURE 2: MESH TOPOLOG

FIGURE 3: VALIDATION AND VERIFICATION OF NUMERICAL SETUP UNDER T06

Full-annulus URANS simulations were primarily conducted for TC range 2. To resolve the RI phenomena and associated flow structures while reducing computational costs, the total mesh count for the full-annulus model was set to approximately 30 million cells. The unsteady calculation was configured with a physical time step equivalent to 20 time steps per rotor blade passing period, with each physical time step advanced using 5 sub-iterations. After validation, this unsteady numerical setup demonstrated the capability to accurately capture both the RI signatures and the evolving flow structures.

2.3 Meridional surface stability prediction model

Following the immersed boundary method, the blade-fluid interaction is modeled via a body force term, so the governing equations for the internal flow within the compressor are as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial (\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot \Pi + \rho \mathbf{f} \\ \frac{\partial (\rho e)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho e \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\Pi \cdot \mathbf{u}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{f} includes the blade-induced force, Π is the second-order stress tensor on the surface of the fluid particle, and e represents the internal energy.

Furthermore, the unsteady terms are decomposed into steady-state components and small unsteady perturbations, thereby linearizing the Eq. (1). Given the circumferential uniformity of the base flow and then the inherent circumferential periodicity of the unsteady perturbations, Fourier expansions can be applied in the azimuthal direction and in time. Ultimately, the meridional surface stability prediction model is following:

$$\left(-i\omega \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + i \frac{1}{r} \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{E} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + \mathbf{G} \right) \tilde{\Phi} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\Phi} = [\tilde{\rho}, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \tilde{p}]^T$. \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{G} are coefficient matrices determined by the steady base flow (more details are in Ref. [25]). Meanwhile $\omega = \omega_r + i\omega_i$ denotes the complex angular frequency, and the imaginary part ω_i is the growth rate of the small perturbation. $\omega_i > 0$ means the amplitude of the perturbation is increasing continuously and the compressor system is unstable. Consequently, Eq. (2) demonstrates that the prediction of flow stability in compressor can be reduced to a large-scale matrix eigenvalue problem.

FIGURE 4: MERIDIONAL SURFACE STABILITY PREDICTION MODEL COMPUTATION GRID

FIGURE 4 illustrates the computational grid of the meridional surface stability prediction model. At the inlet, density disturbance and velocity disturbances are set to zero.

And the outlet boundary enforces zero pressure perturbation. Both the shroud and hub are treated as non-penetration wall boundaries. To validate the meridional surface stability prediction model, SP mass flow rate for TA36 with the original rotor at T06 was obtained through numerical simulation, model prediction, and experimental measurement. As shown in FIGURE 5, the model-predicted growth rate increases monotonically when mass flow rate decreases near stall, and linear interpolation yields a model-predicted SP mass flow rate of 5.42 kg/s. Experimental result indicates that stall onset emerged at 5.47 kg/s, confirming the accuracy of model with a relative error below 1%.

FIGURE 5: VALIDATION OF STABILITY PREDICTION MODEL: STALL POINTS OF ORIGIN UNDER T06

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The original rotor blade of the TA36 compressor is fore-loaded (denoted as Origin). Preserving DP characteristics of TA36, a fully after-loaded rotor blade (AL for short) was developed and demonstrated its superior SM improvement capability under design TC [15]. As schematically illustrated in FIGURE 6, AL demonstrates an increased stagger angle with the location of maximum flow turning proximal to trailing edge, relative to the Origin. These section profiles thus align with that: AL is fully after-loaded along the entire span, while Origin is fore-loaded.

FIGURE 6: ROTOR BLADE SECTION COMPARISON

FIGURE 7 illustrates the variation of experimentally determined SP mass flow rates across TC variation. As TC size increases, the SP mass flow rate increases and the ψ decreases monotonically, indicating the absence of an optimal TC value for

SM and ψ within the investigated TC range. Furthermore, the SP mass flow rate for AL is consistently lower than that of Origin at all TC sizes, demonstrating that AL provides a larger SM across the entire TC range, not limited to the design TC. Concurrently, AL consistently exhibits a higher SP ψ compared to Origin. These combined attributes demonstrate AL's more favorable near-stall characteristics compared to Origin.

FIGURE 7: VARIATION OF SP WITH INCREASING TC. SOLID BLACK LINE FOR MASS FLOW RATE, AND DASHED RED LINE FOR STATIC PRESSURE RISE COEFFICIENT

Within T06-T08, the change in SP mass flow rate for AL is significantly smaller than that for Origin, indicating a desensitization effect of the SP to TC variations within this interval. However, beyond T08, the rate of change for AL becomes comparable to that of Origin.

A detailed analysis of the mechanisms of SM enhancement and SM desensitization to TC will be presented in Section 3.1.

FIGURE 8: COMPARISON OF STEADY CHARACTERISTICS AND RI AT DP FOR DIFFERENT BLD DESIGN ROTOR UNDER T30

RI was observed experimentally within TC range 2, and T30 is selected here for clearer demonstration. FIGURE 8 presents a comparison of the experimental steady characteristics and the spectral analysis of pressure signals at DP for both Origin and AL. Compared to Origin, the performance advantage of AL is evident near the SP. In large mass flow rate region, the

performance of both Origin and AL is consistent. Under T30, the pressure spectra for both configurations confirm the presence of RI. However, compared to Origin, the onset of RI for AL occurs at a significantly lower mass flow rate. Furthermore, at DP, AL exhibits a lower RI frequency (RIF) and a reduced corresponding amplitude compared to Origin.

TABLE 2: VARIATION OF THE DOMINANT CIRCUMFERENTIAL MODE ORDER WITH MASS FLOW RATE AT T30

Dominant circumferential mode order	Origin	AL
Mass flow rate (kg/s)		
7.5	25	26
7.0	22	23
6.4	—	19

TABLE 2 presents the variation of the experimentally observed dominant circumferential mode orders of RI at different mass flow rates under T30. It can be observed that, the dominant mode order decreases with reducing mass flow rate. At identical mass flow rates, the dominant mode order of AL is consistently greater than that of Origin by a value of 1. At a mass flow rate of 6.4 kg/s, the stall occurred for Origin. Meanwhile, the spectrum for AL at this condition does not exhibit a sharp RI peak but rather a broad hump. The dominant mode order for AL under this condition is identified as 19, which is below the rotor blade count of 20. As the mass flow rate decreases, the dominant RI mode order of Origin does not fall below 20. In contrast, AL exhibits a distinct transition, with its dominant mode order transitioning from a value greater than 20 to one less than 20.

A detailed analysis of the associated unsteady characteristics will be presented in Section 3.2.

3.1 TC range 1

3.1.1 Stall point comparison

Within TC range 1, in addition to experimental measurements, a stability prediction model and single-passage steady numerical simulations were employed for in-depth analysis. TABLE 3 compares the predicted SP mass flow rates obtained from these three methods. It can be observed that at T06 and T08, the model-predicted results show close agreement with those of the experiments. In contrast, the RANS results exhibit a significant deviation in predicting the SP. This discrepancy is attributed to the determination of the SP in simulations based on numerical divergence, which is influenced by factors such as the turbulence modeling and numerical viscosity. At T12, the intensified rotor tip flow adversely affects the accurate representation of the base flow by the tip flow region, leading to increased deviation in the model prediction. Overall, however, the model-predicted results remain closer to the experimental data than RANS. Furthermore, the model successfully captures the SM enhancement and desensitization effect demonstrated by AL.

By applying the meridional surface prediction model with the improved algorithm [12], the least stable mode can be

resolved. FIGURE 9 depicts the normalized pressure perturbation modes of the predicted SP mass flow rates under T06 for both compressors. Each pressure perturbation distribution is normalized by its respective maximum amplitude, with each maximum magnitude following the order: Origin > AL. For Origin, the maximum pressure perturbation is concentrated near the rotor tip region, linked to TLF dynamics. This observation confirms that the TA36 is a tip-critical stall compressor, consistent with prior studies [26]. AL exhibits perturbations localized near the leading edge at the tip with narrower spatial extents than Origin. This contraction signifies AL's ability to attenuate tip flow disturbances, contributing to SM improvement.

TABLE 3: COMPARISON OF PREDICTED SP MASS FLOW RATES USING THREE METHODS WITHIN TC RANGE 1

SP mass flow rate (kg/s)	T06	T08	T12
Origin			
EXP	5.47	5.74	5.92
Model	5.44	5.68	6.01
RANS	5.21	5.51	5.88
AL			
EXP	5.21	5.27	5.51
Model	5.11	5.24	5.63
RANS	4.90	5.16	5.48

FIGURE 9: THE LEAST STABLE PRESSURE PERTURBATION DISTRIBUTION AT T06

To elucidate the underlying physical mechanisms while reducing unnecessary comparisons, the subsequent discussion will focus on the results at three key operating points: the DP (7.5 kg/s), the near-stall point (NSP, 6.0 kg/s), and the SP. Furthermore, the least stable mode identified by the meridional stability analysis indicates that the stall inception is linked to flow phenomena in the rotor tip region. Consequently, the

subsequent analysis will primarily concentrate on the blade tip section, encompassing both flow field and BLD analyses.

3.1.2 Rotor tip flow analysis

FIGURE 10 presents the experimentally blade tip pressure contours, alongside the numerically simulated radial vorticity contours and pressure isobars at the 98% span location. The vortex core of the TLV, characterized as a local low-pressure region, is identified on the time-averaged tip pressure contours (left column), with its propagation trajectory indicated by black dashed arrows. In the pressure disturbance contours (middle column), the dominant unsteady region resulting from the periodic rotation of rotor is obscured by the overlaid blade profiles. Significant fluctuating regions outside blade profiles correspond to the interface between TLF and the main flow, marked by red dashed lines and circles for clarity. Within the numerically simulated radial vorticity and pressure isobars (right column), the TLV core and the TLF / main flow interface are similarly annotated using black dashed arrows and red dashed lines, respectively.

FIGURE 10: EXPERIMENTAL TIP PRESSURE CONTOURS, AND NUMERICALLY SIMULATED RADIAL VORTICITY CONTOURS AND PRESSURE ISOBARS OF 98% SPAN

The experimental blade tip pressure contours reveal that as the mass flow decreases, the angle between the TLV and the suction surface (SS) continuously increases. Concurrently, the interface between the TLF and the main flow shifts forward. At SP, the region of maximum pressure fluctuation is located at the plane aligned with the blade leading edges. This indicates that the interface between the TLF and the main flow has become parallel to the plane formed by the blade leading edges, which subsequently triggers stall inception.

The numerical simulation results indicate that, the variation patterns of the TLV and the TLF / main flow interface with decreasing mass flow rate are consistent with the experiment. At both DP and NSP, the TLV trajectory and the general orientation of the interface show good agreement with the experimental data. Furthermore, at SP, the radial vorticity contour at the blade tip also reveals that the region of red radial vorticity (corresponding to the interface) aligns with the plane of the leading edges, which

FIGURE 11: DIMENSIONLESS TLMF AND TLAM DP: (a)(c); NSP: (b)(d)

is consistent with the experimental findings. Consequently, the numerical simulations are validated to accurately capture the evolution of the tip flow field within TC range 1, despite the discrepancy between the numerical divergence point and the experimental SP.

It should be noted that, AL causes the TLV to develop further away from the pressure surface (PS) of the adjacent blade when going downstream in the passage—an effect that becomes more pronounced as the mass flow rate approaches the SP. Furthermore, AL reduces the intensity of the TLV and confines its spatial extent. These combined effects contribute to a lower SP mass flow rate for compressors with spike-type stall inception, thereby enhancing the SM.

Beyond the investigations of flow phenomena and flow structures, a quantitative analysis of the TLF was conducted. The TLF is primarily characterized by two key features: the tip leakage mass flow (TLMF) and the tip leakage axial momentum (TLAM). As demonstrated by Hewkin-Smith et al. [4], rearward migration of the centroid and reduction of the area of TLAM at DP potentially enhance SM. The TLAM is defined as [27]:

$$\text{TLAM} = \left(\int_{R_{\text{tip}}}^{R_{\text{shroud}}} (\rho v_{\theta} A) v_z dR \right) / (\dot{m}_{\text{inlet}} w_{\text{inlet}}) \quad (3)$$

where v_{θ} represents circumferential velocity of the TLF, A represents area of each grid cell within the TC domain, v_z represents axial velocity component, \dot{m}_{inlet} represents mass flow rate at the compressor inlet, and w_{inlet} represents average axial velocity at the inlet.

FIGURE 11 presents the dimensionless TLMF and TLAM distributions for both rotors, at both DP and NSP across varying TCs. These quantities are normalized by the maximum TLMF and TLAM absolute values recorded at DP under T06 respectively. Two dominant trends are revealed: First, amplitudes of both TLMF and TLAM exhibit monotonic growth with increasing TC. Second, reducing mass flow rate from DP to NSP not only enlarges both amplitudes, but also drives an obvious forward shift of their distribution peaks toward the leading edge. Crucially, under identical operating conditions, AL induces systematic rearward shift in TLF distribution and demonstrates significant amplitude suppression relative to Origin. Enlarged TCs intensify TLMF, concurrently increasing TLAM and shifting its distribution forward—all factors detrimental to flow stability. After-loaded design promotes relatively more chordwise-uniform TLF distributions, leading to aerodynamic unloading on the blade tip leading edge and improving flow instability.

Notably, while the NASA E³ Rotor B exhibits TLAM predominantly distributed in the negative half-axis [4], the both rotors of TA36 display complex bidirectional TLAM

distributions with both positive and negative values. This complexity precludes straightforward assessment of SM trends, based solely on directional changes in TLAM area or centroid position. Nevertheless, the magnitudes of variation in the absolute TLAM area and centroid position are feasible to serve as indicators of SM variation, specifically reflecting the degree of sensitivity in stall mass flow rate to TC changes. TABLE 4 quantifies area and centroid changes at NSP during TC transitions, where + denotes area increase or centroid rearward shift, and - indicates area decrease or centroid forward shift. The data demonstrates that, AL displays the minimal area variation (1.359) and the smallest centroid displacement (-0.0418) at T06-T08 interval. This attenuated response correlates with the smallest SM change of AL, revealing the mechanism of its experimentally validated desensitization effect from the view of TLF parameters.

TABLE 4: AREA AND CENTROID CHANGE OF ABSOLUTE DIMENSIONLESS TLAM AT NSP

NSP	T06~T08	T08~T12
Change of Area		
Origin	1.804	3.970
AL	1.359	4.204
Change of Xc		
Origin	-0.0998	-0.0742
AL	-0.0418	-0.0722

3.1.3 BLD analysis

The BLD of tip region fundamentally governs the formation and development of the TLF. Therefore, the underlying mechanisms for SM enhancement and desensitization to TC can also be traced back to the BLD. Subsequently, the relative static pressure at the 98% span location is selected to analyze the BLD, with the reference pressure set at 101,325 Pa.

FIGURE 12 illustrates the BLD for both rotor configurations under T06 and T08. At DP, increasing the TC from T06 to T08 leaves the BLD largely unchanged. Furthermore, AL exhibits significantly lower loading near the leading edge compared to Origin (even displaying negative values in this region), while demonstrating higher loading over the rear portion of the chord, which is consistent with its after-loaded design philosophy. As the mass flow rate decreases from DP to NSP, it is evident that the loading near the leading edge increases. This elevated loading intensifies the strength of the forward jet flow near the blade tip leading edge, thereby promoting stall inception. At NSP, the BLD of Origin undergoes noticeable changes near the leading edge with increasing TC. In contrast, the BLD of AL remains essentially constant along the entire chord length. A minimal variation in tip loading implies a reduced change in the TLF characteristics due to TC variation. For compressors with spike-type stall inception, this manifests directly as a desensitization of the SP to TC.

FIGURE 12: 98% SPAN BLD AT T06 AND T08. (a)DP; (b)NSP

FIGURE 13 compares the BLD of the two rotor configurations at NSP under T06 and T12. Setting Origin as a reference, AL achieves a significant rearward shift in the loading distribution, even under the combined challenging conditions of the enlarged T12 size and the NSP operating condition. Concurrently, TC enlargement intrinsically induces rearward tip loading migration, as demonstrated by the BLD of Origin, which is consistent with prior research [18]. However, a critical distinction must be drawn between this TC-induced rearward tip loading shift and blade after-loaded design. The former arises from intensified TLF induced by increasing TC (see in FIGURE 11), which simultaneously enlarges TLMF and transverse velocities. Although reduced SS-side pressure in the rear of chord shifts loading rearward, the concomitant TLF intensification around leading edge causes catastrophically destabilizing. Consequently, TC enlargement increases SP mass flow rate in tip-critical compressors like TA36, and reduces intrinsic SM. In contrast, the after-loaded design fundamentally circumvents these adverse effects. This design strategy deliberately redistributes circulation toward trailing edge, leading to attenuated TLV strength (see in FIGURE 10), rearward-shifted and more chordwise-homogenized TLF distributions (shown in FIGURE 11), and particularly amplitude suppression of TLF. Thus, the after-loaded design results in SM enhancement collectively, without compromising intrinsic compressor flow stability.

FIGURE 13: BLD COMPARISON OF AT NSP BETWEEN T06 AND T12

3.2 TC range 2

To further investigate the impacts of different BLD designs on RI observed during experiments (refer to FIGURE 8), this section is dedicated to analyzing the full-annulus URANS results, the fundamental setting of which is detailed in Section 2. The analysis focuses on the case under T18 at a mass flow rate of 6.6 kg/s. Under these specific computational conditions, discernible RI signatures were identified in both rotor configurations.

3.2.1 RI propagation

FIGURE 14 presents the unsteady tip pressure spectra for Origin and AL under T18 at 6.6 kg/s. The RIF and its corresponding amplitude of AL are significantly lower than those for Origin. This trend observed in the URANS is consistent with the experimental analysis (see FIGURE 8). RI can be conceptually described as the circumferential propagation of unsteady pressure fluctuations [22]. Consequently, its primary characteristics are the propagation characteristics (including dominant circumferential mode order and the propagation speed), and the source fluctuation. The dominant circumferential mode order corresponds to the mode with the highest energy content during the circumferential propagation of the RI. And the propagation speed is derived from the frequency difference between adjacent RI peaks in the spectrum (a schematic illustration is provided in FIGURE 14).

TABLE 5 further summarizes the analysis results of the unsteady tip pressure signals from the URANS. Besides the RIF, AL also exhibits differences in the dominant circumferential mode order and its propagation speed compared to Origin. The dominant mode order for Origin is 22, which is higher than the rotor blade count of 20. In contrast, the dominant mode order for AL is 17, which is lower than 20. This trend is consistent with the experimental data analysis presented in TABLE 2. Furthermore, the propagation speed for Origin and AL blades are 17.6 Hz and 21.5 Hz, respectively. The product of the dominant mode order and the propagation speed for both cases is less than

the blade passing frequency (BPF), indicating that the RI propagates in the direction of rotation with a speed slower than the rotor rotational speed. Although the propagation speed of RI for AL is greater than that for Origin, the significantly lower dominant mode order of AL results in a substantially lower RIF. This reduction in RIF, achieved by altering the BLD design, is beneficial from an engineering perspective as it helps to avoid critical resonant frequency ranges.

FIGURE 14: UNSTEADY TIP PRESSURE SPECTRA OF URANS

TABLE 5: WALL PRESSURE FREQUENCY SPECTRUM AROUND THE URANS LEADING EDGE POINT

RI characteristics at 6.6kg/s	Origin	AL
RIF (% BPF)	47.4	31.0
Dominant circumferential mode order	22	17
Propagation speed (Hz)	17.6	21.5

FIGURE 15 presents the static entropy contours at 90% span for both rotor configurations at a representative time instant. The entropy distribution remains qualitatively similar at any time, propagating circumferentially while evolving temporally. The region enclosed by the black dashed box will be used for subsequent velocity and pressure analysis. It can be observed that the static entropy contours for both Origin and AL are primarily concentrated on the PS side of the blade passage and exhibit distinct spatial periodicity in the circumferential direction. The yellow dashed lines mark the spatial start of each circumferential cycle (this does not indicate the direction of propagation). The flow field of Origin exhibits entropy distributions corresponding to 2 circumferential periods, which decay towards the leading edge during propagation. In contrast, AL exhibits 3 circumferential periods, which develop and expand towards the trailing edge. The static entropy distribution inherently reflects the underlying flow structure, which is linked to the dominant mode order. For Origin, the interaction between the 2-circumferential-period flow structures and the 20 rotor blades results in a dominant mode order of 22. Conversely, for AL, the interaction between the 3-circumferential-period structures and the 20 rotor blades yields a dominant RI mode

FIGURE 15: STATIC ENTROPY DISTRIBUTION AT 90% SPAN

FIGURE 16: PRESSURE CONTOURS AND VELOCITY VECTORS AT 90% SPAN. IN VELOCITY VECTORS, WHITE SOLID ARROWS DENOTE NON-NEGATIVE AXIAL VELOCITY; BLACK / GRAY SOLID ARROWS REPRESENT REVERSE FLOW (NEGATIVE AXIAL VELOCITY). ARROW LENGTH SCALES WITH VELOCITY MAGNITUDE.

order of 17. Furthermore, the spatial extent of the high-entropy region for AL is noticeably smaller than that for Origin. This also indicates the superior capability in organizing the flow field of AL, which contributes to the suppression of the RI signal amplitude.

Entropy intrinsically reflects the degree of order within a flow: a higher static entropy signifies a more disordered flow state. Therefore, to gain deeper insight into the instantaneous tip flow field with RI, the analysis integrates the pressure distribution and velocity vectors in the tip region, as illustrated in FIGURE 16. The specific passages under investigation in FIGURE 16 are indicated by the black dashed box in FIGURE 15. It is evident that the pressure contours and velocity vectors also reveal circumferential flow structures similar to those identified in the static entropy contours. This consistency across different flow visualizations confirms the coherent, spatially periodic nature of the unsteady flow structures associated with RI.

Analysis of FIGURE 16 reveals that for Origin, the low-pressure region near the trailing edge (indicated by the black dashed circle) correlates with the high-entropy zone in the static entropy contour. The flow in this region exhibits a negative axial velocity, indicative of reverse flow. Furthermore, the fore-loaded design of Origin results in higher loading over the front portion of the blade tip. This leads to an interaction between the TLF emanating from the mid-chord section of the upstream rotor blade tip and the main flow, in addition to the TLV. This interaction induces a reverse flow region near the inlet of Passage ①, marked by the red dashed circle. The presence of reverse flow near the outlet of Passage ① causes the mid-chord TLF

from the subsequent blade to be deflected towards the leading edge. Consequently, the reverse flow zone near the inlet of Passage ② is shifted closer to the leading edge, as the red dashed arrow. This configuration also promotes the upstream migration of the reverse flow near the outlet of Passage ② towards the leading edge, as the dark dashed arrow. This cascading effect further causes the reverse flow region at the inlet of Passage ③ to migrate even further forward, eventually merging with the reverse flow associated with the TLV. Simultaneously, the reverse flow zone near the outlet of Passage ③ is also driven further towards the leading edge. This self-reinforcing, circumferentially propagating mechanism explains the formation of the periodic circumferential flow structure observed for the fore-loaded Origin under RI condition.

In FIGURE 16, the after-loaded design (AL) results in higher loading over the rear portion of the blade tip, which consequently strengthens the TLF passing through the rear portion of the blade tip. This intensified TLF generates a high-entropy zone near the trailing edge in the passage immediately upstream of Passage ①. This TLF further induces a localized reverse flow region near the mid-chord area within Passage ① (marked by the black dashed circle). However, the presence of this reverse flow region in Passage ①—albeit with low velocity—perturbs the formation of the PS-side TLF originating from the rear part of the blade tip. This perturbation causes the reverse flow zone in Passage ② to be located further rear axially compared to its position in Passage ①, as the dark dashed arrow. This self-influencing mechanism propagates circumferentially, explaining the distinctly different evolution of

the circumferential flow structure for AL compared to Origin, arising directly from their contrasting BLD designs.

3.2.2 RI fluctuation

Based on the propagation speed and dominant mode order presented in TABLE 5, the propagation time period of the calculated dominant mode order can be determined. This derived period is confirmed by the URANS. The unsteady computation was configured with 20 time steps per blade passing period, using the time increment ΔT as the fundamental unit. The propagation period is $T_{\text{propagation, origin}} = 33 \Delta T$ for the 22-mode of Origin, and $T_{\text{propagation, AL}} = 42 \Delta T$ for the 17-mode of AL, respectively. The static entropy contour within each flow passage returns to a qualitatively similar pattern after each corresponding propagation time period.

Beyond the propagation, the RI itself undergoes fluctuation. Consequently, the instantaneous flow field is simultaneously influenced by both the propagation and the fluctuation of RI. To isolate the effect of fluctuation from pure propagation, the tip vortex structure can be examined at time intervals corresponding to the $T_{\text{propagation}}$. This approach allows for the identification of the time period associated with the fluctuation $T_{\text{fluctuation}}$. FIGURE 17 compares the evolution of the tip flow field at these propagation-period intervals for the two rotor blades. Here, the swirl angle is defined as the arctangent of the ratio of circumferential velocity to axial velocity, with negative values indicating regions of reverse flow. It should be noted that, for clearer visualization of the changes in the tip vortex structure, only 1-2 instants are shown for each stage of the fluctuation cycle. This presentation does not imply the actual duration of each stage within the full fluctuation cycle. The fluctuation period is determined to be $T_{\text{fluctuation, Origin}} = 11 T_{\text{propagation, origin}} = 363 \Delta T$ for Origin, and $T_{\text{fluctuation, AL}} = 10 T_{\text{propagation, AL}} = 420 \Delta T$ for AL, respectively.

FIGURE 17: EVOLUTION OF TIP VORTEX DURING ONE RI FLUCTUATION PERIOD

FIGURE 17 illustrates that during the fluctuation period $T_{\text{fluctuation}}$, both Origin and AL undergo similar stages of

evolution. The cycle initiates at Stage 0, characterized solely by a distinct TLV. Stage 1 manifests as the splitting of the TLV and an Induced Vortex (IV), accompanied by the attenuation and dissipation of the TLV. Subsequently, the IV also attenuates during Stage 2. Stage 3 is marked by the re-generation of the TLV, and the disappearance of the IV, or alternatively, the merging of the IV and TLV, ultimately returning the flow to the Stage 0 state dominated by the TLV. Compared to Origin, AL exhibits a shedding of the TLV at Stage 0 that is not significantly twisted. Furthermore, the separation between the TLV and IV during Stage 1 is more clearly defined for the AL blade. Overall, the fundamental nature of the RI fluctuation under large TCs is similar for both Origin (froe-loaded) and AL (after-loaded). However, the tip vortex of AL indicates a more organized flow structure. Consequently, as seen in the unsteady pressure spectrum of FIGURE 14, AL exhibits purer spectral peaks with lower amplitudes.

4. CONCLUSION

This study systematically investigated the influence of BLD on flow stability under varying TCs, focusing on SM and RI, by integrating experiment, stability prediction model, and numerical simulation. Within TC range 1, the stability prediction model provided more accurate predictions of the SP mass flow rate compared to RANS, and offered theoretical insights into the role of tip flow disturbances in stall inception. Within TC range 2, both experiment and URANS consistently captured effects of the after-loaded design on RI, particularly the unique occurrence of a dominant circumferential mode order lower than the blade count for AL. The principal conclusions are as follows:

- 1) AL effectively reduces the leading edge loading near the tip, thereby weakening the TLF and promoting a more axial-uniform distribution. This mechanism underlies its superior SM enhancement capability.
- 2) Within T06-T08, AL maintains a relatively stable BLD as clearance increases. This robustness results in minimal variations in the value of the absolute TLAM area and its centroid, thereby achieving the observed SM desensitization to TC.
- 3) Compared to Origin, the onset of RI for AL occurs at a significantly lower mass flow rate. Meanwhile, AL significantly reduces the dominant circumferential mode order of RI to a value below the rotor blade number. The corresponding circumferential flow structure and its propagation pattern differ from those of Origin, as analyzed. Furthermore, despite a similar propagation speed to Origin, AL achieves a substantial reduction in the RIF. Additionally, owing to its superior flow-organizing capability, AL exhibits a significantly lower amplitude of RIF compared to Origin.

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